

ЕКСПЕРИМЕНТАЛЬНІ ДОСЛІДЖЕННЯ ВПЛИВУ ПАРАМЕТРІВ СВІТЛОВОГО СЕРЕДОВИЩА НА ФУНКЦІОНАЛЬНИЙ СТАН ПРАЦІВНИКІВ

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EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES OF EFFECTS OF THE LIGHT ENVIRONMENT PARAMETERS ON THE FUNCTIONAL STATUS OF EMPLOYEES

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Анотація

Вступ. Трансформація змісту та обсягу роботи працівників у сучасному виробництві потребує якісного енергоефективного світлового середовища постійних робочих місць в приміщеннях. Водночас спостерігається світова тенденція поширення зорових хвороб серед працездатного населення.

Проблематика. Зміна умов праці за показниками напруженості трудового процесу на виробництві та підвищення рівня відповідальності за результати діяльності збільшують ризик помилкових дій внаслідок погіршення функціонального стану людини. Для забезпечення зорової працездатності чинне законодавство встановлює нормативні параметри світлового середовища в приміщенні. Дотримання зазначених норм буває проблематичним при реконструкції старих виробничих приміщень, а підтримання нормативних показників на належному рівні практично не контролюється з часом. Залежність показників функціонального стану операторів від кількісних параметрів світлового середовища, як фактора трудового процесу, потребує подальших досліджень.

Мета. Встановлення діапазону параметрів світлового середовища щодо забезпечення оптимального та високого рівня функціонального стану працівника на постійному робочому місці в напруженій праці.

Матеріали і методи. Методика експериментальних досліджень обґрунтована загальною концепцією освітлення робочих місць в приміщеннях із визначенням факторів впливу на працездатність людини. Рівні функціонального стану працівників в залежності від параметрів світлового середовища (джерело світла, освітленість робочої поверхні, колірна температура) досліджувалися за методикою визначення психоемоційної реакції на навантаження в умовах трудового процесу на діючому підприємстві з виготовлення та продажу металевих виробів.

Результати. Оптимальний та високий рівень функціонального стану працівників при штучному освітленні робочого приміщення люмінесцентними лампами зафіксовано в діапазоні 500-800 лк при колірній температурі 5400-6000 К. При освітленні світлодіодними лампами отримано кращі результати, які відповідають діапазону 500-1000 лк та колірній температурі 4500-6500 К.

Висновки. Індивідуальні особливості психоемоційної реакції на навантаження в різних системах освітлення мають загальну тенденцію – підвищення активності зі зростанням освітленості при одночасному зниженні психоемоційної напруги. Проведені дослідження зміни суб'єктивних оцінок працездатності операторів в залежності від параметрів світлового середовища (рівень освітленості, колірна температура) підтверджують значний вплив показників освітлення на психофізіологічний стан працівника, і, як наслідок, на працездатність та безпеку праці оператора.

Abstract

Introduction. Transformation of the content and scope of employees' work in modern production requires a high-quality energy-efficient light environment of permanent workplaces in premises. At the same time, there is a global trend of the spread of eye diseases among the able-bodied population.

Range of problems. Changing job conditions upon indicators of intensity of the labor process at production site and rising the level of responsibility for the results of activities increase the risk of erroneous actions due to the fact that the functional status of a person is getting worse. In order to ensure visual performance, the current legislation sets regulatory parameters of light environment indoors. Compliance with these standards is occasionally problematic in reconstruction of old production facilities, and maintenance of regulatory indicators at the appropriate level is virtually uncontrolled over time. The dependence of indicators of operators' functional status on the quantitative parameters of light environment as a factor of the labor process requires further research.

Purpose. Establishment of a range of the light environment parameters to ensure the optimal and high levels of an employee's functional status at a permanent workplace in hard-working.

Materials and Methods. The methodology of experimental studies is based on the general concept of lighting the workplaces indoors with the definition of factors influencing the human work capacity. The levels of employees' functional status depending on the light environment parameters (light source, illumination of work surface and color temperature) were investigated in line with the method, at which the psycho-emotional response to stress was determined in conditions of the labor process at the operating enterprise for manufacturing and selling metal products.

Results. The optimal and high levels of the functional status of employees under artificial lighting of work premises with fluorescent lamps were recorded in a range of 500-800 lux at a color temperature of 5,400-6,000 K. The better results corresponding to a range of 500-1,000 lux and a color temperature of 4,500-6,500 K were obtained under LED lighting.

Conclusions. Individual features of the psycho-emotional response to stress in different lighting systems have a general tendency: – increment in activity as the degree of illumination rises with the concurrent decrease in the psycho-emotional stress. The conducted studies of changes in subjective assessments of operators' work capacity depending on the light environment parameters (level of illumination, color temperature) confirm the significant effect of lighting indicators on the psycho-physiological condition of an employee and, consequently, on the work capacity and occupational safety of an operator.

Ключові слова: світлове середовище, зорова працеспроможність, функціональний стан працівника, працездатність, безпека праці.

Keywords: light environment, visual performance, functional status of an employee, work capacity, occupational safety.

The permanent workplaces of employees (operators, managers) in modern production are protected [13] from hazardous and harmful factors of the industrial environment, such as noise, dust, vibration, radiation, chemicals and aerosols, since their work is performed in premises remotely located or isolated from core operations. Therefore, the main factors measuring the level of job conditions are work intensity, microclimate and light environment. As a rule, microclimate inside such premises meets hygienic requirements, since it is provided with technical equipment of heating, ventilation and air conditioning. Conversely, less attention is paid to creating a comfortable and safe light environment at the permanent workplaces.

The influence of lighting conditions on health, work capacity and occupational safety of a person has been confirmed by the papers of European and domestic scientists [8, 10, 22, 15, 21, 4, 9, 20]; there has been established a downward tendency of a number of accidents with increasing levels of illumination. In Ukraine, the increase in diseases of an eye and its appendage amounted to 131.1% among the able-bodied population

over the past 10 years [2-3]. Studies by ophthalmologists and hygienists confirm the linkage between the growth of eye diseases and poor-quality artificial lighting, which leads to overstress of the visual analyzer, increased errors and, consequently, upward risk of a dangerous situation.

Range of problems. In recent years, job conditions have changed significantly both in terms of indicators of intensity of employees' labor process at production site (content of work, sensory and emotional stress) and luminaire solutions for lighting their workplaces indoors. As a result of increasing the level of responsibility for the results of activities, erroneous actions of employees entail the risk of industrial hazards, whose implementation may be an accident, injury or breakdown of service. In different types of production activities, the number of accidents related to unsatisfactory lighting is 30-50% of the total number on average.

The current regulatory documents [17, 6] contain requirements not only for the level of illumination, but also for indicators of lighting quality. However, it should be noted that compliance with these standards

can be difficult in reconstruction of old production facilities (e.g., lack of light slots) and, what is more important, maintaining the standard indicators at the appropriate level is virtually uncontrolled over time.

In modern production of various industries, the share of managers, specialists, technicians, and workers for the maintenance and operation of equipment has increased. Analysis of the content of activities being carried out by this category of employees (operators) enables to establish the following common features: perception of information by the visual analyzer on monitors of terminals and computers, processing and reproduction of information handled, and decision-making. Relevant job conditions [18, 5] are characterized by monotony and intensity; the requirements for speed of perception and processing of information, attention concentrating, critical thinking, and responsibility for decision-making, where errors can have significant negative man-triggered consequences, are raised [12].

Analysis of job conditions according to the classifier of occupational titles of employees, who manage or control the process, revealed the kindred characteristics of labor intensity: sensory, intellectual, emotional stress and decision-making, which afforded ground for studies of changes in indicators of the functional status of operators depending on the quantitative parameters of light environment as a factor of industrial space and as a factor of the labor process by its particulars.

Purpose. Establishing a range of the light environment parameters (level of illumination and color temperature) in dependence to light source in order to ensure the optimal and high levels of an operator's functional status at the permanent workplace, taking into account work intensity in the modern labor process.

Substantiation of the studied lighting systems. The content and features of operational activities involve the permanent presence of an employee at the workplace, so such kind of premises must have natural lighting, para.6.1 [17]. Combined and artificial lighting are used for production and auxiliary premises subject to shortage of natural lighting in order to ensure work capacity according to the nature of works being performed [17, 6].

Natural lighting. Creation of a safe light environment is impossible without natural light coming to the work surface, but its use is limited by light and climatic conditions of the region. Thus, when determining a daylight factor in November in experimental premises with a depth of 4.5 m and a width of 3 m and a window of 2.2x1.5 m, in a characteristic section at a distance from the light hole (point A-1 m), (point B-2 m), and (point C-3 m) respectively, the level of natural lighting in latitude 48°27'00'' North was distributed over time, from 8.00 am to 03.00 pm, in a range shown in Table 1. Later, employees were forced to use artificial lighting. This confirms the need to provide a high-quality artificial lighting indoors throughout all working hours.

Table 1

Example of distribution of the natural lighting levels in experimental premises depending on the time-of-day (November), Dnipro

Time-of-day, 48°27'00'' North	External horizontal lighting E_{3G} , lux	Level of natural lighting on the work surface		
		E_A	E_B	E_C
8 am	6,300	263	141	98
9 am	7,900	265	180	132
10 am	9,500	429	226	157
11 am	11,100	503	249	182
12 pm	11,500	516	266	186
01 pm	10,700	483	250	173
02 pm	8,000	270	184	130
03 pm	5,270	186	89	56

Artificial lighting. Today, fluorescent lamps are common in Ukraine for general lighting of workplaces. Significant advances in development of compact fluorescent lamps have made it advisable to use this light source for the arrangement of local lighting at workplaces, if there is a shortage of natural light. Among the various types of lighting in the field of industry, the leader in developed countries is LED. The main advantages of CD-technologies include their environmental safety due to the absence of mercury and energy efficiency, since the introduction of modern LED solutions reduces energy consumption for lighting by up to 70%.

The studies [14, 7] analyzed the degree of observers' fatigue depending on conditions of the general level of lighting in dynamics. It was found that in the ratios of natural lighting and artificial one provided by discharge lamps, in case of artificial lighting being increased, fatigue had been growing. A number of studies

has confirmed [11, 23, 19] that the shortwave light leads to a phase shift of the circadian system and distress of melatonin secretion. This increases the feeling of vitality and activates the functional status of the body; thus, for the responsible and focused work, it is necessary to take into account this aspect. For the inactive work, it is better to use warm-white lighting, where the maximum visual sensitivity concentrates in the yellow-green area.

Substantiation of experimental studies

Study Methodology. The general concept of indoor lighting [4] determines three areas of the possible influence of light environment on visual performance: time-of-day, individual features of an employee (age, functional status) and work intensity (content of work, workplace lighting). We identified a factor space for studying the functional status of employees at the permanent workplace taking into account the most significant effects.

Factor I: time-of-day. We take the influence of time-of-day based on the known studies [15, 9, 20, 16]. Physiologists take into account effects of the circadian system grounded on the rhythms of human life activities (dependence of activity on the spectrum of solar radiation and illumination on the eye retina). Vigorous human activities occur during the day hours from 8.00 am to 06.00 pm, which is a working time for the majority. Therefore, it is advisable to conduct studies exactly during this period.

Factor II: individual features of an employee. This factor is defined by psychologists as mood, expectations of the results of actions and motivation. The study involved men and women aged from 20 to 60 years old.

Factor III: work intensity. Visual and mental performance, fatigue, motor activity, cognitive performance and visual discomfort are taken into account. The main indicators of an operator's work intensity are: the continuative attention (or density of signals), degree of risk to their own lives and degree of responsibility for others' lives.

For studying the functional status of employees by the factor of light environment, the HAM (health, activity, mood) technique was chosen, which is common

to determine the psycho-emotional response to stress (work intensity). The studies were conducted in real production conditions. The advantage of the industrial experiment is to obtain results by establishing levels in real conditions of the operating process of existing lighting systems.

The method of the HAM operational self-assessment is to test an employee during working hours. H is health consisting of strength, soundness and fatigability. A is activity, which is determined by mobility and speed of the body functions. M is mood composed of characteristics of the emotional state. The HAM Test [1] is a table containing 30 pairs of polar features that reflect the traits of a person's psycho-emotional state. Each state is represented by 10 pairs of words, such as 'at full strength – exhausted' for health, 'sedentary – lively' for activity, and 'cheerful – sad' for mood. There is a 7-point rating scale (3 2 1 0 1 2 3) between the polar characteristics. An employee is proposed to determine the severity of any of characteristics of his state in the form of one of the scores on the scale. The score 0 corresponds to the average (neutral) state (of health or response). The levels of the functional status f were determined according to Table 2.

Table 2

Levels of the functional status of operators f according to HAM

Low	Permissible	Optimal	High	Very High
$f \leq 4$	$4 < f \leq 5$	$5 < f < 5,5$	$5,5 < f \leq 6$	$f > 6$

The advantage of the HAM technique is the ability to study the dynamics of an employee's functional status through repeated tests, as well as to establish a correlation between the psycho-emotional response to stress and age groups or working hours.

The generality of characteristics (lack of details of individual features) makes it possible to obtain the dependence of operators' state on the parameters of light environment (light source, level of illumination, color temperature).

The influence of light environment on the functional status of an employee was studied in the systems of natural lighting, and artificial lighting with fluorescent and LED lamps. The level of illumination and color temperature were measured while testing with Chroma Lightmeter ST520 device. The parameters of light environment were recorded directly on the work surface three times during the experiment. When processing the results, the level of illumination was taken as the arithmetic mean value of three dimensions.

Approbation of the technique. The experimental studies of employees were conducted at the enterprises of metallurgical and construction industries of Dnipro Region, whose workplaces were located in separate premises. The content of work was to solve simple alternative tasks according to the instruction, perception of signals (information) and their assessment with subsequent decision-making. The job conditions involved

performing the work pursuant to the established schedule with its possible adjustment in the course of activities; attention should have been in the state of concentration for more than 75% of working hours.

The tests were conducted anonymously (only the age and content of work were recorded). The operators worked with the test 3 times for 15 minutes on average. The testing period was selected according to the work schedule (from 8.00 am to 04.30 pm with a break from 12.30 pm to 01.00 pm):

- The first test was conducted from 8.00 am to 9.00 am: – the stage of warming-up;
- The second test was conducted from 11.00 am to 12.30 pm: – the stage of high capacity for work;
- The third test was conducted from 03.30 pm to 04.00 pm: – the stage of fatigue.

The valid and most representative results were selected among the surveys: – 100 tests in total.

The results of self-assessment of an operator's functional status at the workplace under natural lighting that range within the levels from 80 to 450 lux are presented in Figure 1. Analysis of the scattering pattern shows that the well-being of most respondents at the normalized levels of illumination corresponding to 300 lux [17] and 500 lux [6] falls within the range from the minimum permissible level to the optimal one, i.e. operators feel comfortable at the workplace.

Fig. 1. Self-assessment of the functional status of an operator at the workplace under natural lighting.

The high level (4.8-5.6) of the functional status is fixed at the values of illumination exceeding 300 lux. This self-assessment is conditioned by the physiology of visual perception, since the human eye is best adapted to natural light (brightness contrast, color difference, image quality on the retina, and illuminating intensity on the retina). At the same time, the levels of activity and mood are assessed by employees as low: – permissible for the entire range of measurements. This is probably related to the reduced circadian efficiency [15] of lighting.

Significant scattering of the results of the functional status self-assessment is observed under artificial

lighting (Figure 2) with the use of fluorescent lamps. The low level of activity, as under natural lighting, was found in the range of 80-450 lux, as well as from 800 lux and more. The highest activity is observed in the range of 500-800 lux, which confirms the indirect effect of light on the physiological condition of a person. The health level, from low to permissible one, was recorded at illuminations of up to 100 lux and more than 850 lux. However, the optimal and high levels of health as well as mood are expressed by the accumulation of data from 450 lux to 750 lux, so the increase in working efficiency is observed.

Fig.2. Self-assessment of the functional status of an operator at the workplace under artificial lighting with the use of fluorescent lamps.

At artificial lighting with the use of light-emitting diodes, there is observed a convergence of the results of testing health, activity and mood (Figure 3). The low level of activity, mood and health was found in the range of the high levels of illumination from 800 lux

and more, while the permissible-optimal one is in the range of 250-500 lux and 700-800 lux. At the levels of illumination from 500 lux to 700 lux, there is the accumulation of data of the high level of an employee's functional status.

Fig.3. Self-assessment of the functional status of an operator at the workplace under artificial lighting with the use of LEDs.

The results of studies of employees' functional status depending on the color temperature are also presented in the form of scattering patterns. When testing under artificial lighting with the use of fluorescent lamps, the color temperature varied in the range from 4,500K to 6,100K (Figure 4). The largest amount of

data on the high level of operators' functional status is observed at the color temperature of 5,400-6,000 K. This is confirmed by both high work capacity of an operator and self-assessment of the functional status of an employee, except for individual features conditioned by the psychological component of labor.

Fig.4. Self-assessment of the functional status of an operator at the workplace under artificial lighting with fluorescent lamps depending on the color temperature.

The increased work capacity is observed at the color temperature ranging from 4,500K to 6,500K of artificial lighting with the use of LEDs (Figure 5). In the same way as at artificial lighting with fluorescent lamps, the vast majority of data of the high level of an employee's functional status was recorded at illumination from 500 lux and more with the color temperature of $5,500 \pm 250$ K. At artificial lighting with LED

lamps of about 1,000 lux, the HAM indicator is at the low and sufficient levels, in contrast to lighting in the range of 500-700 lux, where this figure is optimal and high. Therefore, the level of illumination at the permanent workplaces of operators should be around 700 lux with a minimum of 500 lux, which is confirmed by the European Standard, but the National Standards offer a minimum level of illumination of 400 lux [17].

Fig.5. Self-assessment of the functional status of an operator at the workplace under artificial lighting with LED lamps depending on the color temperature.

Results of Studies. The experimental studies were conducted in the period from January 2018 to December 2021 at the enterprise for manufacturing and selling metal products, at the permanent workplaces of operators-managers (men and women) of the production department. The permanent workplaces are located in premises with an area of 12 m², 18 m² and 24 m². The microclimatic conditions are optimal (temperature: 21–24°C, humidity: 40–60 %, air velocity: 0.2 m/s). The premises are equipped with heating and air conditioning appliances, and provided with natural light in sufficient amount (the area of windows is not less than 30 % of the total area). The options for lighting the workplaces are natural, combined and artificial. The work of operators-managers with elements of monotony and intensity is mostly performed on personal computers

(monitors). The characteristic of visual works corresponds to B-1, A-1.2 [17]. The studies of changes in the functional status of employees depending on the parameters of light environment were conducted according to the developed methodology.

There are three workplaces of employees in the office for accounting and delivery of products from the warehouse with a total area of 18 m² (Figure 6). The content of their work is to solve simple alternative tasks according to the instruction, perception of signals (information) and their evaluation using a PC (Visual Work Category B-1). The further study of the functional status depending on the sources and levels of lighting was conducted directly at the workplaces. The normalized minimum level of illumination [17] is 300 lux.

Fig. 6. Indoor disposition of the workplaces of employees from the office for accounting and delivery of products from the warehouse

In the period from mid-October to March 2017-2021, the employees used artificial lighting throughout the whole working day. The results are given in Tables

3 and 4 conformably to natural and artificial lighting with fluorescent lamps.

The results of studies of the functional status of employees are the low level of activity (Table 4). We recommended replacing fluorescent lamps with LED

ones. After the recommendations had been implemented, the better results of the functional status were obtained (Table 5), and the proposed system of light environment provided the level of illumination in the

range of 510-550 lux. Such illumination of the workplaces provides the high level of the functional status of employees.

Table 3

Results of studies conducted under natural lighting at the workplaces of operators from the office for accounting and delivery of products from the warehouse

Working hours	Workplace	Level of lighting, lux	Operational self-assessment			Level of the functional status f_{cep}
			H	A	M	
8.00 am-9.00 am	1	180	3.9	4.2	5.3	$f_{cep} = 4.5$ - permissible
	2	100	5.1	3	3.3	$f_{cep} = 3.8$ - low
	3	92	4.9	3	5.8	$f_{cep} = 4.6$ - permissible
11.00 am-12.00 pm	1	650	6.1	6.5	6	$f_{cep} = 6.2$ - very high
	2	600	5.8	6.3	5.3	$f_{cep} = 5.8$ - high
	3	530	5.5	4.9	5.2	$f_{cep} = 5.2$ - optimal
03.00 pm-04.00 pm	1	210	5.2	4.8	5.1	$f_{cep} = 5$ - optimal
	2	170	3.9	3.1	4	$f_{cep} = 3.7$ - low
	3	100	5.1	3	3.3	$f_{cep} = 3.8$ - low

Table 4

Results of studies conducted under artificial lighting with fluorescent lamps at the workplaces of operators from the office for accounting and delivery of products from the warehouse

Working hours	Workplace	Level of lighting, lux	Operational self-assessment			Level of the functional status f_{cep}
			H	A	M	
03.00 pm – 04.00 pm	1	225	4	3.9	5.1	$f_{cep} = 4.3$ - permissible
	2	230	4.4	4	3.9	$f_{cep} = 4.1$ - permissible
	3	180	3.9	4.2	5.3	$f_{cep} = 4.5$ - permissible

Table 5

Results of studies conducted under artificial lighting with LED lamps at the workplaces of operators from the office for accounting and delivery of products from the warehouse

Working hours	Workplace	Level of lighting, lux	Operational self-assessment			Level of the functional status f_{cep}
			H	A	M	
03.00 pm-04.00 pm	1	550	6.7	6	6.8	$f_{cep} = 6.5$ - very high
	2	542	6.7	6	6.8	$f_{cep} = 6.5$ - very high
	3	510	6	6.4	6.1	$f_{cep} = 6.2$ - very high

Premises of managers from the production department.

There are three workplaces in the room with a total area of 18 m² (Figure 7). Their light environment is natural lighting, and artificial lighting with the use of fluorescent lamps.

Fig. 7. Disposition of the workplaces of managers from the production department (photo taken under artificial lighting with fluorescent lamps)

The content of their work is to solve complex tasks by choice as per the algorithm and to work according to a series of instructions, as well as to perceive signals followed by comparison of actual values with their nominal ones; and processing, checking and monitoring the performance of a task. Their work is done in the conditions of time shortage with information falling

within the scope of enhanced responsibility for the end result. The normalized minimum level of lighting at the workplaces is $E_H = 500$ lux. The generalized results of studies of the functional status in the systems of natural lighting and artificial lighting with fluorescent lamps are given in Tables 6 and 7.

Table 6

Results of studies conducted under natural lighting at the workplaces of managers from the production department

Working hours	Workplace	Level of lighting, lux	Operational self-assessment			Level of the functional status f_{cep}
			H	A	M	
8.00 am – 9.00 am	1	330	4.9	5.1	3.7	$f_{cep} = 4.6$ – permissible
	2	440	5.6	2	5.9	$f_{cep} = 4.5$ – permissible
	3	450	5	3.1	4.8	$f_{cep} = 4.3$ – permissible
11.00 am – 12.00 pm	1	780	5.5	5.6	6	$f_{cep} = 5.7$ – high
	2	762	4.7	5.8	4.9	$f_{cep} = 5.1$ – optimal
	3	850	5.4	6	5.7	$f_{cep} = 5.7$ – high
03.00 pm – 04.00 pm	1	300	5	2.5	5.6	$f_{cep} = 4.4$ – permissible
	2	282	5.1	5.2	4	$f_{cep} = 4.8$ – permissible
	3	270	5	4	5.8	$f_{cep} = 4.9$ – permissible

Table 7

Results of studies conducted under artificial lighting with fluorescent lamps at the workplaces of managers from the production department

Working hours	Workplace	Level of lighting, lux	Operational self-assessment			Level of the functional status f_{cep}
			H	A	M	
03.00 pm – 04.00 pm	1	330	4.2	4	3.7	$f_{cep} = 4$ – permissible
	2	345	4	4.9	4.6	$f_{cep} = 4.5$ – permissible
	3	410	4.7	2.5	5.7	$f_{cep} = 4.3$ – permissible

Taking into account the degree of intensity of the labor process and requirements for the high level of activity, it is proposed to replace fluorescent lamps with LED ones in lighting fixtures, and to paint the walls in the premises in a light color.

After implementing the recommendations (Figure 8), the system of artificial lighting with LED lamps ensures the level of lighting in the range of 700–770 lux, which corresponds to the high and permissible functional levels of employees.

Table 8

Results of studies conducted under artificial lighting with LED lamps at the workplaces of managers from the production department

Working hours	Workplace	Level of lighting, lux	Operational self-assessment			Level of the functional status f_{cep}
			H	A	M	
03.00 pm – 04.00 pm	1	700	4.8	5	3.9	$f_{cep} = 4.6$ – permissible
	2	721	6	5.4	5.9	$f_{cep} = 5.8$ – high
	3	770	6.9	6.1	6.3	$f_{cep} = 6.5$ – very high

Fig. 8. Disposition of the workplaces of managers from the production department (photo taken under artificial lighting with LED lamps)

Conclusions based on the results of studies.

1. The experimental studies have shown a decrease in the parameters of light environment at the permanent workplaces when performing the visual works B-1, A-1.2 from the normalized minimum levels of illumination by more than 10%.

2. Recommendations were developed for the improvement of quality of the lighting system, which allowed meeting the requirements of the European Standards for workplace lighting [6].

3. The proposed recommendations for workplace lighting are based on the results of studying changes in the functional status of operators depending on the parameters of light environment.

General Conclusions.

1. Establishing a range of the light environment parameters to ensure the optimal and high levels of the functional status of an employee at his permanent workplace in hard-working is based on the general concept (4) of visual performance of an operator with the definition of impact factors.

2. To determine the psycho-emotional response to stress during the performance of functional duties at the workplace, the technique for the operational HAM self-assessment was used, which is attributed to the industrial experiment techniques in occupational psychology. The advantage of the industrial experiment is that the established levels of the functional status correspond to real conditions of the production process and parameters of lighting systems at workplaces.

3. Analysis of the results has shown that the individual features of the psycho-emotional response to stress in different lighting systems have a general tendency of increment in activity as the degree of illumination rises (above the normalized minimum level) with the concurrent decrease in the psycho-emotional stress. The conducted studies of changes in subjective assessments of operators' work capacity (health, activity, mood) depending on the parameters of light environment (level of illumination, color temperature) confirm the significant effect of lighting indicators on the psycho-physiological condition of an employee, and, consequently, on work capacity and occupational safety of an operator.

4. The expediency of using LEDs to create an effective light environment at an operator's permanent workplace has been confirmed.

5. Analysis of the obtained quantitative data as per the ratio of levels and sources of lighting against the level of an operator's functional status allows establishing a range of the parameters of light environment, which not only provide the high visual performance, but also contribute to raising the level of occupational safety. The results obtained by the technique described above do not restrict the freedom to choose a particular lighting system and use innovative equipment, but enable to select a system that is the most favorable one for solving production problems at high quality standards.

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